

(0.5 × 0.5 m interplant space) were collected.

For the hybrid program, we are

synthesizing one population for irrigated rice and one for upland rice. The long stigma of the wild

allogamous species *Oryza longistaminata* is being introduced in these populations. □

Cytogenic relationship between two cytoplasmic male-sterile lines

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Cytoplasmic-genetic male sterility (CMS), conditioned by the interaction of nuclear and cytoplasmic factors, is used extensively in hybrid breeding programs for self-pollinated crops. Hybrid varieties grown commercially in China are derived mostly from cytoplasmic sources of wild rice *Oryza sativa* f. *spontanea*, designated as WA (wild rice with aborted anthers). Alternative sources of cytotosterility are needed to protect F₁ hybrids against potential genetic vulnerability to diseases and insects.

We have developed a new CMS (A) line, IR54755A, which has the cytoplasm of land race ARC13829-16 introduced from Assam, India, and the nuclear genotype of elite breeding line IR10179-2-3-1. Another CMS line, IR46828A, was developed in the same nuclear genotype with the WA cytoplasm from Chinese CMS line Zhen Shan 97A. We studied the cytogenic relationship between the two cytotesterile lines developed from the two different cytoplasmic sources.

Each CMS line was crossed with its maintainer and single plant selections of a number of other maintainers,

Pollen fertility behavior of F₁ progenies between CMS, maintainer, and restorer lines. IRRI, 1986 dry season.

Male parent	Female parent											
	IR46828A					IR54755A						
	Plants (no.)	F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class ^a					Plants (no.)	F ₁ plants (no.) in pollen fertility class				
	CS	S	PS	PF	F		CS	S	PS	PF	F	
IR54755B	19	19	0	0	0	0	48	48	0	0	0	0
IR46828B	49	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0
IR46829B	9	7	2	0	0	0	10	10	0	0	0	0
IR46830B	8	8	0	0	0	0	10	10	0	0	0	0
IR36R	9	0	0	0	0	9	8	0	0	0	2	6
IR46R	9	0	0	0	0	9	10	0	0	0	0	10
IR64R	6	0	0	0	0	6	10	4	3	1	2	0
IR9761-19-1R	6	0	0	0	0	6	6	0	0	0	1	5
IR28	9	0	0	0	0	9	9	0	2	0	3	4
IR34	5	2	2	1	0	0	10	9	1	0	0	0
IR43	10	6	4	0	0	0	10	5	3	2	0	0
IR52	8	0	0	0	0	8	10	0	0	0	0	10

^a pollen fertility classes: cs = completely sterile, 0% pollen fertility; s = sterile, 1-10% pollen fertility; PS = partially sterile, 11-30% pollen fertility; PF = partially fertile, 31-60% pollen fertility; F = fertile 61-100% pollen fertility.

restorers, and partial restorers of the WA cytotesterility system. The F₁ population of these crosses was evaluated for pollen fertility using 1% IKI solution.

The maintainers of the two CMS lines (IR54755B and IR46828B) effectively maintained the male sterility in the two cytotesterile lines (see table). However, IR64R, IR9761-19-IR, IR28, IR34, and IR43 showed differential fertility in crosses with the two CMS lines.

These results indicate that the cytoplasmic factors inducing male sterility in IR46828A and IR54755A may be different. The maintainers IR46828B and IR54755B, derived from the line IR10179-2-3-1, have genotypes capable of maintaining both cytotesterility systems. The cytogenic differences observed here need to be substantiated by analysis of mitochondrial DNA of the two CMS lines. □

Survival of some F₁ rice hybrids and their parents in saline soil

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Increased vegetative and root vigor are useful traits to use in adapting rice plants to soil and climatic stresses. Usually, F₁ hybrids express these traits. We evaluated 12 F₁ rice hybrids

and their parents for survival in saline soil at IRRI in the 1986 dry season. Although the hybrids' parents are not known to be tolerant of salinity, our objective was to test the usefulness of hybrid vigor under such stresses as soil salinity.

Five-wk-old seedlings grown on wet seedbeds were transplanted at 50 hills/entry in a field where salinity to an EC of 7 dS/m had been induced by

adding common salt. Check varieties were IR28 (salt sensitive) and IR9884-54-3 (salt tolerant). The field salinity level was maintained throughout the experiment. Plant survival was recorded at 6, 12, and 15 wk after transplanting.

Salinity prolonged the growth duration of all varieties tested. Very early parents and hybrids flowered about 100 d after seeding.